

MULTISCALE EDGES DETECTION ALGORITHM IMPLEMENTATION USING FPGA DEVICES

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ABSTRACT

One of the way to extract edges uses the fast wavelet transform algorithm. This technique allows the detection of multiscale edge and is used to detect all the details which are in a picture by modifying the scale. The real time application for edge detection involves the implementation of the algorithm on an integrated circuit like an FPGA and the development of an appropriated board. This article deals about the implementation of a wavelet transform algorithm onto a FPGA and the development of an electronic board to detect multiscale edges.

1 INTRODUCTION

The image processing using the wavelet transform can be applied to the multiscale edges detection. In this way Mallat [1] introduces a fast wavelet algorithm using spline functions. We use the Mallat algorithm but using the generalised Deriche filter [2][3] and this to take advantages of the good Signal-to-Noise Ration performances of this filters.

With this algorithm, a four scale edges detection needs 32 filters third-order recursive filters (for a scale we need two detection filters and two smoothing filters).

We present in this paper a real time parallel implementation of our algorithm using FPGA devices.

2 FILTERS AND ALGORITHM DESCRIPTION

We can define a wavelet as a function $\psi_s(x)$ satisfying the condition $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \psi_s(x) dx = 0$ where s represents the scale parameter. We can also introduce a scaling smoothing function $\phi_s(x)$ satisfying the condition that $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \phi_s(x) dx = 1$. These wavelet and smoothing 1-D functions are realised using the generalised Deriche filters [3] :

$$\psi_s(x) = \begin{cases} C_s \cdot (k_0 s x e^{m s x} + e^{m s x} - e^{s x}) & x \leq 0 \\ C_s \cdot (k_0 s x e^{-m s x} - e^{-m s x} + e^{-s x}) & x > 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\phi_s(x) = A_s \cdot [(k_0 m s^2 |x| - k_0 s + m s) e^{-m s |x|} - m s^2 e^{-s |x|}] \quad (2)$$

with k_0 and m which are the adjustable parameters for the good detection, good localization and one response to one edge. These filters give an optimum Noise-to-Signal Ratio (NSR) and localization for $k_0 = -0,564$ and $m = 0,215 \forall s$.

In the 2-D signals case, we can consider separable filters in x and y directions and in consequence we can define two masks x and y : $M^x = \psi_s(x)\phi_s(y)$ and $M^y = \phi_s(x)\psi_s(y)$.

For fast numerical implementations, the scale parameter is made to vary along a dyadic sequence $\{s = 2^j | j \in Z\}$. A dyadic wavelet transform of an image $f(x, y)$ is described by the convolution between an image and the two masks x and y . This convolution is shown by the following relations:

the X wavelet component

$$W_{2^j}^x f(x, y) = f(x, y) * (\psi_{2^j}(x), \phi_{2^j}(y)), \quad (3)$$

the Y wavelet component

$$W_{2^j}^y f(x, y) = f(x, y) * (\phi_{2^j}(x), \psi_{2^j}(y)), \quad (4)$$

and the vector gradient

$$W_{2^j} f(x, y) = \sqrt{|W_{2^j}^x f(x, y)|^2 + |W_{2^j}^y f(x, y)|^2}. \quad (5)$$

The X and Y wavelet transforms correspond respectively to the X and Y gradients of the image and the vector gradient represents the edge of image. Then we can use the wavelet transform for multiscale edge detection by the scale j modification.

The following algorithm represents a dyadic wavelet transform for multiscale edges detection.

for $j = 0$ and $j > J$

$$W_{2^j}^x f(m, n) = (f(m, n) * \Psi_{2^j}(z)) * \Phi_{2^j}(z)$$

$$W_{2^j}^y f(m, n) = (f(m, n) * \Phi_{2^j}(z)) * \Psi_{2^j}(z)$$

$$W_{2^j} f(m, n) = \sqrt{|W_{2^j}^x f(m, n)|^2 + |W_{2^j}^y f(m, n)|^2}$$

end for.

with $\Psi_{2^j}(z)$ and $\Phi_{2^j}(z)$ which are the numerical filters of the $\psi_{2^j}(x)$ and $\phi_{2^j}(x)$ filters. Their Z transform derives

two recursive filters moving in opposite directions :

$$\Psi_{2^j}^+(z) = \frac{a_1 Z^{-1} + a_2 Z^{-2}}{(1 - \gamma Z^{-1})^2 (1 - \beta Z^{-1})} \quad (6)$$

$$\Psi_{2^j}^-(z) = \frac{a_1 Z + a_2 Z^2}{(1 - \gamma Z)^2 (1 - \beta Z)}, \quad (7)$$

$$\Phi_{2^j}^+(z) = \frac{c_0 + c_1 Z^{-1} + c_2 Z^{-2}}{(1 - \gamma Z^{-1})^2 (1 - \beta Z^{-1})} \quad (8)$$

$$\Phi_{2^j}^-(z) = \frac{c_3 Z + c_4 Z^1 + c_5 Z^2}{(1 - \gamma Z)^2 (1 - \beta Z)}. \quad (9)$$

with $a_1, a_2, c_0, c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, \gamma$ and β are the numerical coefficients of the filters (table.1 and 2). These two Z-transforms correspond to two rational system transfer functions of stable third-order recursive filters from the left to the right (Ψ^+ and Φ^+) and from the right to the left (Ψ^- and Φ^-).

In particular, for example the output sequence $y(m)$ in response to $x(m)$ as input to a system, with impulse response $\psi(m)$, can be obtained recursively according to :

$$y_{2^j}^+(m) = a_1 \cdot x(m-1) + a_2 \cdot x(m-2) + b_1 \cdot y_{2^j}^+(m-1) - b_2 \cdot y_{2^j}^+(m-2) + b_3 \cdot y_{2^j}^+(m-3)$$

$$y_{2^j}^-(M-m) = a_1 \cdot x(M-m-1) + a_2 \cdot x(M-m-2) + b_1 \cdot y_{2^j}^-(M-m-1) - b_2 \cdot y_{2^j}^-(M-m-2) + b_3 \cdot y_{2^j}^-(M-m-3)$$

and

$$y_{2^j}(m) = y_{2^j}^+(m) + y_{2^j}^-(m) \quad (10)$$

for $m = 0, \dots, M$

with $b_1 = 2 \cdot \gamma + \beta$, $b_2 = 2 \cdot \gamma \cdot \beta + \gamma^2$, $b_3 = \gamma^2 \cdot \beta$ and M denoting the length of $x(m)$.

We denote as for each scale j , the algorithm (equations 3, 4 and 5) computes the edge of the original image. Then we can use this algorithm for parallel multiscale implementation. The following images represent the results of multiscale edges obtained by this algorithm.

Figure 1.(a) Original image

(b) Edge for $j=3$

(c) edge for $j=2$

(d) Edge for $j=1$

(e) edge for $j=0$

The figures 1.(b), (c), (d) and (e) show the edges results of the noisy image (figure 1.(a)). We remark as if the scale j is large, the edges are very good localized but the noises are present. If the scale j is small, the noises are very good filtered and we have the edges very large. These edges results in the four different scales j obtained by the wavelet transform allow to detect all the detail informations present in a picture.

3 FILTER IMPLEMENTATION

In this section we present the implementation methods for the computation acceleration and the minimization of the circuitry surface. We propose a cascade transpose structure to implement our filter [4]. The equation (6) can be composed :

$$\Psi_{2^j}^+(z) = (a_1 + a_2 z^{-1}) z^{-1} \frac{1}{(1 - \gamma z^{-1})} \frac{1}{(1 - \gamma z^{-1})} \frac{1}{(1 - \beta z^{-1})} \quad (11)$$

and its implementation structure is shown in figure (2). This structure gives an acceleration. The computation time is $T_{multiplication} + T_{addition}$ ($T_{multiplication} + 4 \cdot T_{addition}$ for classic structure implementation).

Figure (2). Cascade transpose implementation structure

For the minimization of the circuitry surface, we propose to implement the filters with the coefficients as constants. We choose the optimal case of the filters (equations 1 and 2 for $k_0 = -0.564, m = 0.215$) and we fix the scale $j = 0, 1, 2, 3$. In this case the numerical coefficients of the filters are interpreted as constants (tables 1 and 2) and this allows us to simplify the arithmetic operations in particular for the multiplication operations.

j	m	γ	β	a_1	a_2
0	0.21	0.8109375	0.3678794	0.0547381	-0.0320587
1	0.211	0.65625	0.1353352	0.1051479	-0.0368287
2	0.216	0.421875	0.0183156	0.3805066	-0.0519443
3	0.22	0.171875	0.0003355	0.7075226	-0.0022245

table 1.

CONCLUSION

We implemented the four filters $\Psi_{2^j}^+(z)$, $\Psi_{2^j}^-(z)$, $\Phi_{2^j}^+(z)$ and $\Phi_{2^j}^-(z)$, in the Xilinx FPGA 4005-PG156 device by using our methods. These filters use between 85%-90% of the FPGA surface.

We realized an image processing board in the goal to edges detection in real time (10 MHz per pixel for an image of 512 x 512 pixels) as it is shown on the figure (5).

The four scales edges detection allows to increase the quality of the detection in the case of blur and noisy images. Thus in consideration with the good edge detection quality in real time, we intend to use our system in industrial and medical applications.

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Figure (5). Real time multiscale edges detection system developed. 1. The original ilage, 2. Our real time image processing board, 3. The result of the edges by our board system, 4. The real time of Roberts gradient system box, The result of the edges by Roberts gradient system.